

Generation of meaty flavour compounds from Maillard origin under mild conditions simulating the dry curing process

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Abstract

The flavour of dry cured meat products is generated under mild temperatures at long ripening periods. In these conditions, the generation of dry cured aroma compounds from Maillard reactions is unknown. The aim of this study was to evaluate the generation of volatile compounds under mild curing conditions simulating the drying process of fermented sausages. Three model systems labelled initial (I), 1st drying (1D) and 2nd drying (2D) containing different concentrations of amino acids and curing additives, as well as different pH and a_w values, were incubated at different temperatures. The flavour profile was investigated by SPME-GC-MS and the amino acid content was measured by GC-FID. Four compounds detected, dimethyl disulphide, 3-(methylthio)propanal, thiazole and methylpyrazine, were the source of meaty-roasted aromas among seventeen volatile compounds identified in the model systems. The production of dimethyl disulphide and 3-(methylthio)propanal was related to the Strecker degradation of methionine. Thiazole and methylpyrazine increased significantly during the incubation time, although this increase was significantly higher when the model systems were incubated at 37 °C. The presence of methylpyrazine was favoured by presence of lysine and high pH values. This research demonstrates that at mild curing conditions volatile compounds are generated via Maillard reactions from free amino acids. The a_w of model systems resembling the 1st and 2nd drying stages together with the presence of free amino acids was essential for the formation of meaty flavour compounds.

Keywords: Maillard, meat, dry curing, water activity, amino acid

Introduction

Meat flavour formation in dry cured meat products is still a challenge, despite the numerous efforts to describe many savoury aromas [1]. The nitrogen-containing and sulphur-containing compounds are essential for development of meaty aroma in these products. However, the participation of the Maillard reaction (MR) in the formation of dry cured meat flavour is not well known [2, 3]. The mechanisms involved in the formation of meaty flavour compounds in dry fermented sausages and the influence of the physicochemical conditions such as pH and low temperature are poorly comprehended. For this reason, generation of aroma compounds from three model systems containing amino acids and additives (NaCl, nitrate/nitrite, ascorbate, glucose) in composition similar to dry sausages [4] were investigated under the physicochemical conditions (pH, a_w and temperature) simulating the initial, first drying and second drying stages of the sausage manufacture [5]. The model systems were incubated at 25 °C and 37 °C and the meaty aromas formed from the degradation of methionine, lysine and glycine were examined during 35 days of incubation. This study examines the generation of meaty aroma compounds in model systems resembling dry fermented sausages under mild curing conditions.

Experimental

Three different model systems (Table 1) were prepared according to the concentration of additives and free amino acids at the initial (I), 1st drying (1D) and 2nd drying (2D) stages of the process [6]. Phosphate buffer at 0.2 mM was used to adjust the pH, while glycerol was used to adjust the a_w at the different processing stages. Sterilization was done by filtration using a 0.2 µm filter (Sartorius, Göttingen, Germany), and incubation was performed at 25 and 37 °C. Samples from each media and temperature were taken at different times (0, 5, 11, 15, 20, 25, 29 and 35 days) for volatile and amino acid analyses.

Analysis of Volatile Compounds

The analysis of volatile compounds generated during the incubation of models was carried out in a gas chromatograph with a quadrupole mass spectrometer detector GC-MS (GC 7890 series II, MS 5975C, Agilent Palo Alto, CA, USA). For volatile extraction, 5 mL of the model system was placed into a headspace vial and extracted using an automatic sampler Gerstel MPS2 (Gerstel, Germany) by headspace (HS) solid-phase microextraction (SPME) with a 85 µm carboxen/polydimethylsiloxane (CAR/PDMS) fibre (Supelco, Bellefonte, PA, USA).

Before extraction vials were equilibrated at 37 °C for 30 min and then, volatile compounds were adsorbed into the fibre for 60 min at 30 °C and desorbed in the injection port of the GC–MS for 5 min at 240 °C in splitless mode. The volatile compounds were separated using a DB-624 capillary column (30 m, 0.25 mm i.d., film thickness 1.4 µm (J&W Scientific, Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA) using the conditions described by Corral et al. [7]. The MS interface temperature was set to 240 °C. The compounds were identified in full scan mode and by comparison with mass spectra from the library database (Nist'05), with linear retention indices [8] and using authentic standards. The quantitation was performed in SCAN mode using total ion current (TIC) and expressed as abundance units (AU) $\times 10^6$.

Table 1: Composition of model systems resembling the dry curing stages.

Dry curing stages	Initial stage (I)	1 st drying stage (1D)	2 nd drying stage (2D)
pH	5.45	4.38	4.6
Aw	0.968	0.944	0.895
NaCl (mg/ml)	27	27	27
NaNO ₂ (mg/ml)	0.15	0	0
NaNO ₃ (mg/ml)	0.15	0.1	0.075
Sodium ascorbate (mg/ml)	0.5	0.5	0.5
Glucose (mg/ml)	20	5	5
Glycine (mg/100ml)	10.94	33.06	42.58
Methionine (mg/100ml)	2	33.99	36.27
Lysine (mg/100ml)	6.82	77.55	120.9

Analysis of Amino Acids

The analysis of free amino acids was performed using the EZ-Faast kit (Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA). Model system samples were diluted with distilled water at ratio 1:5 (v/v) for I stage, and 1:25 (v/v) for 1D and 2D stages previously to derivatisation and norvaline was added as the internal standard. The derivatised amino acids were analysed using a gas chromatograph with a flame ionization detector (GC-FID) (GC 7890B, Agilent, Palo Alto, CA, USA) equipped with a liquid autosampler (G4513A, Agilent Palo Alto, CA, USA) and a ZB-AAA column (10 m \times 0.25mm) (Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA). The analysis was done using the conditions described by Li et al., 2021 [6]. Identification and quantification were based on retention time and peak area integration of the reference amino acids. Calibration curves for each amino acid were obtained with the standard amino acids solutions (Phenomenex). Results were expressed in milligrams per 100 mL of model system.

Statistical analyses

The effect of incubation time on volatile compounds and amino acid content was studied by analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the statistic software XLSTAT2018 (Addinsoft, Barcelona, Spain). Principal component analysis (PCA) was plotted to evaluate the relationships between volatile compounds and amino acids in the different models and incubation temperatures.

Results and discussion

Among the volatile compounds detected [6], four compounds, dimethyl disulphide, 3-(methylthio)propanal, thiazole, and methylpyrazine produced meaty-roasted aromas of great impact in dry sausage flavour [1]. The concentration of the amino acids precursors of these volatiles in the model systems (met, gly and lys) were determined, revealing that only met concentration showed a significant decreased during incubation (Figure 1). The highest production of these four aroma compounds was observed in 1D and 2D model systems incubated at 37°C (Figure 2). The high glucose content of the Initial model (I) is not essential for the generation of these volatile compounds, as none of them were produced in high abundances in the I model.

Furthermore, the Strecker degradation of met was related to the production of dimethyl disulphide and 3-(methylthio)propanal. Regarding pH and a_w conditions, model 1D with lower pH and higher a_w than 2D favoured the formation of dimethyl disulfide and 3-(methylthio)propanal. The evolution of 3-(methylthio)propanal was different from the other volatile compounds as it increased with the incubation time until 10 to 15 d, and then it decreased specially in 1D model. Thiazole and methylpyrazine increased significantly during incubation in 1D and 2D models, especially at 10 days of incubation at 37 °C, while at 25°C this increase was detected at longer

incubation times (25 or 30 days). The presence of lys and gly and the low pH values in the models favoured the presence of methylpyrazine, although other factors seem to affect its generation.

In order to examine the relationship between amino acids and flavour compounds generated in the 1D and 2D models a principal component analysis (PCA) was performed (Figure 3). Two principal components were able to explain the 86.47% of the total variability. PC1 accounted for 59.28% of the variability and was strongly related with the incubation time and temperature. Long incubation times and high temperature were located on the left quadrant, while short incubation times and low temperature were on the right. PC2 accounts for 27.20% of the variability and distinguishes samples by model systems and variables (volatile compounds and amino acids). The model systems 2D and variables (dimethyl disulphide, thiazole, methylpyrazine and gly and lys) were on the upper quadrant while on the low quadrant were 1D model and variables (3-(methylthio)propanal and met). It is important to see that 3-(methylthio)propanal is opposite to met while methylpyrazine is opposite to gly and lys. This means that degradation of these amino acids is related with the formation of these compounds as observed for met (Figure 1).

The mild conditions applied were enough to generate aroma compounds in the model systems as observed in other media [9]. However, in dry meat products, as seen in 1D and 2D models, the limiting factor to produce volatile compounds from Maillard reactions is the amino acid content as well as temperature and a_w conditions, while the content of saccharides seems to be no essential.

Figure 1: Amino acid concentration in the model systems (mg/100 mL) during incubation at 25 °C or 37 °C and classified according to the dry curing stages (I-Initial stage, 1D-1st drying stage, 2D-2nd drying stage).

Figure 2: Abundance of volatile compounds in the dry cured model systems (I-Initial stage, 1D-1st drying stage, 2D-2nd drying stage) incubated at different temperatures 25 °C and 37 °C.

Figure 3: Loadings of the first two principal components (PC1-PC2) of model systems simulating the dry curing stages (1D-1st drying stage, 2D-2nd drying stage) and variables (volatile compounds and amino acids).

Conclusion

Generation of meaty flavour compounds under mild conditions has been demonstrated in model systems simulating the dry curing process in terms of amino acid content, pH, a_w and additives. This experiment proved that free amino acids participate in the generation of volatile compounds via the Maillard reaction in addition to the microbial activity in dry fermented meat products. Moreover, the low water activity of models resembling the 1st and 2nd drying stages together with the presence of free amino acids are essential for the formation of meaty aroma compounds in a dry fermented sausage model under mild conditions of processing.

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